

Simone Weil: METAXU:
THE COURAGEOUS WAY TO ACT SIGNIFICANTLY.

1. How to promote and bring about clear and concrete actions for a better world?
2. Today's world is predominated by negative actions, which disables human transcendence.
3. How can we grasp the concrete, practical-ethical choice of a single individual, which precedes any theory?
4. How can we reflect on this problem with the watchword »courage to act«?

This is the first post mortem interview made to Miss Simone Weil,
by KUD Apokalipsa and Centraleuropean Research Institute Soren Kierkegaard Network.

The intention of this paper is to answer questions we are called for in this gathering exactly in Ms. Weil's words. What she said, was never quite listened. Her worries back then are our worries right now.

-Miss Weil: KUD+CRISK network is honored and thank you for this interview. The main concern at this time, and the reason we turn to your legacy is the need to spur ethical action in our rotten societies. We are aware you feel reluctant to refer to your experience as "philosophy" and you rather speak of an intellectual and spiritual path as a call or vocation to "return" to a life that comes from above and should descend down here.

-The issue with these sort of experiences is that they don't let themselves be imprisoned in words, but I will do my best to convey them through. Plato faced the same difficulty¹.

Before myself, Aristophanes mentions in Plato's Banquet, man was cut in half therefore is forever searching for his completion, and so is the soul of the world, in search of fulfillment through illuminated human action². This search seems to be the constant of our time in the world, theirs, mine and yours.

[Ms. Weil laughs and interrupts herself]

I just want to point out this idea of "searching for the other half" means fecundity/fruitfulness/fertility and this can only be either corporeal or spiritual³, which is the REAL thing. The Freudian idea of sublimation could only come forth *au milieu* of the stupidity of my time! I tried to elaborate on this particular matter in my last *escrit L'Enracinement*⁴.

Please continue.

-As I was saying, we want to find out what are the implications of making a balance or critique of our present civilization, to find out in detail why man has become slave of his own creations. How methodological unconsciousness has infiltrated into thought and action? To hide in a life away of civilization is a lazy solution. It is of utmost importance to find the original pact between the spirit and the world inside our own civilization to right the rudder. Even if it seems impossible, due to the brevity of life, and the lack of collaboration and succession among civilizations. This is no reason to stop searching for it: as Socrates when awaiting death in his prison cell, he learned to play the lyre: we can say, at least, we lived⁵... it is no futile attempt.

The interview is structured in 4 linked questions that address the practical-ethical scope of your legacy. We expect many of the notions to be pinned down, as the whole map of action is unveiled. The first question is:

1. How to promote and bring about clear and concrete action for a better world?

-As an introduction I will state some notions, as coordinates, to start out strolling, they shall become clear all along:

There is a reality, out of this world, out of time and space, out of man's mental universe not graspable by human faculties. There is a correspondence in the center of the human heart to this reality: the demand of the Absolute Good that inhabits in this transcendent reality and finds no direct object in this world. It is the appetite of man for GOOD. The reality of this Absolute Good becomes manifested through absurd contradictions and injustices, against which the human mind crashes constantly in this world; the feeling to straighten them out makes it clear. In the same way as reality is the basis of

¹ S.W., *La Connaissance Surnaturelle.*, Gallimard., Paris., 1950. p. 805.

² S.W., *La Pensateur et la Grace.*, Union General d'Editions, "le Monde en 10/18", 1962. p. 160.

³ S.W., *Cahiers III, Plon, Paris, 1956, 1974.* p. 162.

⁴ S.W., *L'Enracinement.* Gallimard., Paris., 1949.

⁵ S.W., *LPG.* p. 152.

facts, so is this transcendent reality the basis of the Good. All the existent Good thereof comes from: Beauty, Truth, Justice, Legitimacy, Order etc., which appeal to the subordination of the human conduct to oblige.

a) The first part of the question calls for pro-motion: move to, towards.

Promotion draws a line between 2 extremes. It calls for a relation; it is not wise to move unless you know where to go. A fertile ground from where to start and a clear goal to reach, are necessary. This goal –means and end- are in the individual realm, to burry it into the collectiveness is a common confusion. So, this is the starting point for clear action: to be clear where to, Attentionness is the first step in order to be strategic.

Plato's myth of the cavern illustrates how we are chained to the shadows of society. Society is the cavern. The way out is solitude⁶, silence: just as the most beautiful music is the one that grants the grave intensity to an instant of silence, the kind that compels the listener to heed silence. Through the enchantment of sound it lead into the silence within him, after that exterior silence is simply added to complete this state of solitude⁷.

This is the first step: to pay attention and separate the rind from the fruit. As prayer is the purest form of attention, and study, its gymnastics: each school exercise should be a refraction of spiritual life. But a methodology is followed: a certain way to do a Greek translation, a certain manner to solve a geometry problem, not any manner but an orderly one, are the proper training to turn the mind apt [...] Tiredness might languish our discursive faculties but not contemplative activity. Contemplation requires a broader scope, which discursive faculties simply cannot provide⁸.

In the same mood, the ascendant path in *The Republic* goes by degrees of attention. The eye of the soul is attention ... Attention that is absolutely pure oriented to God because His presence is real to the extent of attention. Mathematical relations are not much without attention (but still they are something, God is nothing without attention)⁹.

Mathematics leads us to confirm the limits of intelligence: it is always possible to think an unexplainable reasoning because we ignore some of its constituent factors. Here we have all the factors, combined in broad daylight of demonstration and still we cannot understand. In this sense, such as force is in relation to our will, math is in relation to our intelligence. This compels us to turn the gaze of intuition even further. The universe of signs grows in density, and is nevertheless hard¹⁰.

The way to go is beyond: this is Clarity.

The orientation of attention to a broader scope should be sustained by mediation; these means, need not be manufactured, but are discovered embodied in the nature of things, set there in a pro-vidential way. Only those who are paying silent attention, with a contemplative wide-open mind can grasp these means.

-So, if I get it right, the only intermediary by which THE GOOD can descend from its scope to the human realm is through the mediation of the people whose attention and love are oriented to this other reality, which is beyond the discursive faculties¹¹. That is a sort of intuition rather than a premise-conclusion type of reasoning.

- Yes that is right.

When our attention is set out of this world, it comes from the essential structure of the human nature, and only this essential human nature has the perennial faculty of projecting light on the human being. The respect this experience arouses cannot be put into words, language is insufficient, but can be manifested in this world, this is precisely the link: the reality of this world in need and misery, the indirect expression of this respect is the fulfillment of the worldly dissatisfactions of body and soul. This possibility is based on the contact established between human nature: the demand of good, which is the essence, and sensibility. This liaison is present in every man, no matter what circumstances may prevail. Due to this contact, when as a result of omissions or commissions of fellow men, the life of someone is injured, mutilated, destroyed, wounded, or deprived of any need of the soul not only his sensibility is stricken but also his aspiration to the Good. Then, Sacrilege has been committed towards that which is sacred in manhood¹².

-Now we can examine the next part of the question.

Bring about: Every man has this capacity: to execute or materialize his finding, after he has stripped the Good embodied in the ordinary, that is fruit of the relation grasped between this worldly reality and the other superior one. This capacity becomes such, as it is exercised. The only condition to

⁶ Cahiers., p. 231.

⁷ Ibid., p. 129.

⁸ Ibid., p. 239.

⁹ LPG., p. 158

¹⁰ Ibid., p. 141.

¹¹ Cfr. *Ecrits de Londres et Dernière Lettres*, Gallimard, Paris. P. 77-84.

¹² Ibidem.

exercising this capacity is **consent**. This consent can be explicitly formulated, or not be, it may not even be clear to the mind that it has taken place in the soul, many times it has not taken place, even though it has been linguistically expressed. Formulated or not, the one and sufficient condition is that it has taken place¹³ and is anyhow acknowledged. Most of the time, consent is mixed with a lie. When there is not a lie, to bring it about encounters frailty anyhow. That is to say, that to reject, causes criminality. Therefore, the balance between good and evil in a society depends on the proportion on consent and rejection to bring about this good on one hand, and the distribution of power to carry them out, on the other¹⁴.

- So let me rephrase your words, from your point of view, the only means by which the Good can be brought about the world are those persons or intermediaries whose attention and love has enabled them to grasp this other reality. Every man has the capacity to turn his attention towards the Good, even though it is out of reach of the common human faculties.

This ability grows with use and only needs to be consented intimately.

When this sequence of events, takes place, and the foreshadowed crevice of good is materialized, Good descends upon him and enlightens all the human scope around it?

-That is correct.

-But why is rejection of consent the root of criminality?

I do not want to sound harsh but deep down the root, things are fair and square:

If the thirst of Good is what unchains human action, somebody that is endowed with the capacity to foresee, not only his own self-realization as to complete his nature but also has the opportunity to help out his fellow peers to do so, and improving the world, to disregard this call, is criminal. The criminal action consists in wasting human grandeur. Not to live up to his greatness.

I mentioned before, how Aristophanes, in Plato's *Banquet* explains how restful love ends the duality of original sin, each of us is a symbol (sign of recognition established by an object cut in two pieces) Each one searches for his symbol, his other half or completion. Man is cut in two, as is the soul of the world¹⁵.

The amount and type of Good each and every one of us, can bring about to this world is absolutely unique due to our very personal *Weltanschauung*. To turn our back towards the one and only personal contribution to the improvement of the world turns out to be not only antisocial but criminal behavior, or schizophrenic at least, if its not on purpose. (And I despise, as I have said, Freudian approaches).

I am sorry to say this lack of attention and love for others is the common trend of every society that has rotten itself from the inside, we have all experienced this sad fact one way or another.

- Thank you for deepening in this particular topic. We now return to the core of our question: What would you call a **CLEAR ACTION**?

b) Clarity is the needed impulse to reach the goal from the starting point of the relationship to the good. The organ by which we know TRUTH is intelligence; the organ within us by which we see God is LOVE (...) but intelligence must acknowledge through its own means –that is through discursive verification and demonstration-, the preeminence of love¹⁶.

Mysticism must provide the key to all knowledge and to all values¹⁷.

All things are searched and researched not for themselves, but for the good in them. Only the Good is searched for itself, therefore only the Good is absolute¹⁸. In short, what I want to point out is that there is an ascendant line of thought, which harmonically gives way to recognize this intuition of the GOOD as superior and leading.

The right linkage of all these factors is clarity: the starting point for action.

-This seems contradictory, but better put, we could say we wish to know the truth of what we love¹⁹. And this not only sounds right but also is as clear as it is true. Is it not?

- That is exactly the idea. All true Good implies contradictory conditions (grasped by discursive faculties) and is therefore impossible. So the one that is able to maintain fixed on this impossibility and acts through it, will CLEARLY bring about Good²⁰.

¹³ *Ibidem*

¹⁴ *Idem.*

¹⁵ *Cfr. LPG. p. 160.*

¹⁶ *Cahiers II. p. 132.*

¹⁷ *Idem. p. 159.*

¹⁸ *Ibidem.*

¹⁹ *Cfr. L' enracinement. p. 215*

²⁰ *LPG. p. 23.*

Now, according to all that has been said, how is **concrete action** produced?

- We get to the *quid* of the matter, the intercrossing of paths where all previously exposed concepts intertwine: what lies under this interweave of concepts is time or, how is the infinite introduced into the finite?

True Good is sent from heaven in imperceptible amounts, either within each soul or in society, “the seed of mustard is the smallest”, “Proserpine ate but one grenade nugget”, we do not realize the yeast in the dough, also in chemical reactions with catalysts, with bacteria in yeast, and so happens in human things with the imperceptible nuggets of true good operate in a decisive way by its only presence, if we consent to put them where they are needed²¹. This is a matter of opportunity: the right place (clarity) and the right time. There’s no miracle against time. Faith that moves mountains is impotent with time. God has abandoned man in time²². So, concrete action, to be effective has to artfully weave the infinite/impersonal with space and time, this comes forth subordinating all human faculties to the goal that will materialize the captured glimpse of good we feel capable of constructing: that is our obligation. I have named this confluence of elements **METAXU**, a Greek adverb, and modifier of time, which means in-between. With this volatile concept I want to describe the evanescent nature of our contribution to the good in the world. *Metaxu* is a transformation operated in the soul when the possibility of inserting the infinite into our *quotidienne* opens up: space and time take a new form. Space takes, in relation to what was in it embryonically in a cubed infinity, and the instant is motionless, immobile²³. Time stops and eternity is apprehended here and now. In this infinity of infinite, a deep silence prevails; it is not only absence of sound but also a positive object of sensation, more real than sound, which is the secret word, the word of love that holds us in his arms since the beginning²⁴. This socio-cultural concretion of this superior light is the interval of *metaxu*, it appoints to the temporary and human realities which enable and sustain the satisfaction of the fundamental needs of being human in the world, and the fulfillment of man’s superior vocation: they are the bridges, the intermediaries for an upward path, they are active realities, assumed, lived, desired and loved. It is by inspiration that they arise on a certain place at a certain time, in specific social forms where need has not yet destroyed that delicate and frail breeding ground for the development of the soul. It is about how the worldly outruns evil, in a specific time and space, where the mindset of one individual improves, the world. To do this, every human being must be integrated in culture, education, profession, social environment, and homeland in order for the roots to bear fruit. *Metaxu* nurtures the flowering terrain of a sensible human life. They work as bridges between God and man²⁵.

- *Metaxu*: interesting concept Ms. Weil: is it a sort of in-between state in which time and space extrapolate? Is being *metaxu*, to become a passage of light, in which superior Good can travel into the world in a specific time and space to a concrete intention, illuminating the world?

-Yes, more or less that is *Metaxu*.

-We can finish the first question if you can share your concept of a better world.

- After all I have said we do have several core concepts to describe a better world. *Metaxu* are relative goods, intermediate supports that work as springboards to project the soul towards the Absolute Good and to let the Good-Absolute-Love descend to the creatures. They are the places and the environment that introduce human attention to that two way movement. This is the reason why they are of capital importance in the fulfillment of a healthy community life. In order for these relative goods to play their essential role inside the social life and display the spiritual experience of each performer it is important to respect them, desire them, love them and promote them. Men in society must recognize their essential part, and serve it. There is no need to introduce the absolute in the relative, on the contrary, an absolute **obligation** does exist to build up these relative goods that are *metaxu*. “We must accept the given situation which subjects us to absolute obligations towards the relative, limited and imperfect things. To learn to discriminate which things are those and their demand of obligation, it will suffice clearly see what is its relation to the Good”²⁶.

These absolute obligations towards relative things are all the density and gravity of concrete existence, the value of existence, which we shall not elude if we intend not to fail in our ascension to

²¹ Cfr. *ELeDL*, p. 40-44.

²² S.W., *La Connaissance Surnaturelle*, Gallimard, Paris. 1950. pp. 91-92.

²³ Cfr. S.W., *Attente de Dieu*, Fayard, Paris 1966. pp. 48-49.

²⁴ *Ibidem.*, p. 49.

²⁵ Cfr. Springstead E., *Metaphysics of Transcendence and the Theory of Metaxu*, in *Cahiers Simone Weil*, T. No. 4, December 1982.

²⁶ *EL*, p. 138.

God. "Because it is only through the things and beings from down here, that human love can penetrate what is beyond"²⁷.

He who contacts with the supernatural is king by right, because he is a worthwhile presence in society, under the mode of the infinitely small, of an order that transcends the social scope. But his place within the social hierarchy is irrelevant. In his spot, he is the center of gravity. For a soul in balance, the center of gravity is immobile²⁸.

Under this light, we shall conclude that we are the instruments by which the divine presence is truly present in the world, in this sense, it is the principle that orders the universe extended through a huge subterranean network of relationships²⁹. The more Divine Providence is in the world, the better the world is.

- You have been most eloquent. Thank-you. We'll have a 2-minute pause for sponsors and continue with the next questions.

- Now we are back, and after this very philosophic approach to you experience we'll proceed to analyze the ethical and social complications of today's societies.

The next question we would like you to answer for us is:

2. Today's world is predominated by negative action, which disables human transcendence. How can we grasp the concrete, practical-ethical choice of a single individual, which precedes any theory?

- We have to speak about the political conformation of the world. It is in the realm of the relative means, where man is resourceful. But how are these resources administered and how does these relationships develop?

The world is the *lieu* of necessity therefore it can't offer Absolutes, it can only offer relative means thus, our incessant longing of Good bounces from one mean to another like a billiard ball³⁰.

Modern collectives are mainly built as democracies -whatever is understood by this very elastic notion- and these democracies are founded by a series of rights, in some countries these are conquered, in others granted. Either way, rights are linked to quantity, commercial exchange, and especially to force and thus can be misused, abused and corrupted. This opens a big space for violence, and leaves very little space for justice and caritas (not charity), therefore this kind of arrangement is alien to the Good. No wonder, Plato spoke of politics as "the great Beast" and Locke as "the Leviathan"³¹. The most dangerous screen of the collective are political parties, incapable of silence they can only hear their own noise, and they give no hearing to truth and human misery. Political parties exert pressure on the judgment of its members; they circumscribe the first and last analyses to their own growth. They also fabricate collective passion, which is another way to turn off the brain end put external pressure to their members.

When political parties rule collectives, a reversion between means and ends take place, as the quest is for money, power, estate, nationalism, economic productivity, diplomas, etc.

A political party is in principle an instrument to serve a certain conception of good, its action field is facts, and as collective thought cannot go beyond facts, it takes the Absolute Good as a mean. Means or partial goods, are poor social connectives, no wonder societies malfunction. Only the Absolute Good is an end³².

As a consequence of this lack of thought, parties are in a perpetual state of impotence, and think this is due to the insufficient power exercised at the moment: if it had the whole country, they would think international needs would impose narrow limits on it, anyway.

Exactly as if the party were beef cattle and the whole universe its grazing field³³.

Consequently, political parties are always totalitarian *ad intra* and *ad extra*. The public good, for all parties, is a mere fiction that imposes the search of total power: that which does not exist can't be limited; therefore there is an affinity between totalitarianism and lie: the revolutionary trend leads to totality; the *petite bourgeoisie* trend leads to an image of unlimited progress, in both cases these lies exert a collective stress on the thought of men. In any case, the only valid criterion is the material growth of the party. We must be aware that if a criteria other than good is held, the notion of Good is lost³⁴. There is no room for effective intervention in public affairs if the game of political parties is not played. Those who care for the public good either resign to think about it and indict their actions

²⁷ *Idem.*, p. 137.

²⁸ *Cfr. Cahiers.*, pp. 109-113.

²⁹ *Cfr. L'Enracinement.*, p. 330 ss.

³⁰ *Cahiers.*, p. 121.

³¹ *Cfr. EL.*, pp. 11-44.

³² *Ibidem.*

³³ *EL.*, p. 130.

³⁴ *Idem.* pp. 126-130.

elsewhere, or undergo the torture of politics. The influence of parties has finished with thought and reflection (life of the spirit) of our times.

Political parties are a mechanism by which, throughout any country, not even one mind spares attention to the effort to discern on public affairs: Good, Truth, Justice. Resulting –safe in in very rare and random coincidences- only public measures against the public good are decided and executed. It shall also be said that the Catholic Church in its quest against heresy introduced this perverted mechanism, armed with the arm of excommunication.

But, the worse part is not the collective's tendency to compress the individual, the real danger comes from the inside, the individual's tendency to immolate, to drown himself in the collective, while others think for him, just as T.V. does in your time.

I see the law as the fire inside Plato's cavern, projecting those confusing shadows. The collective is the cavern. Collective life is the Leviathan if it is not referred and relegated in all human dimensions to the Good.

Or maybe the worst peril is really, the apparent and deceptive aspect of the second. If it were useless, as it is, to tell the collectivity that the human is sacred, more useless would be to tell the human person he is sacred, if he can't feel it. In this sense, it is useful to remember that, no generalization in the personal aspect is possible; it is a mistake to do so. Anonymous human matter can't hold virtue; this is absolutely a unique experience in each individual³⁵.

Anybody that sets his attention and love, in the higher reality, acknowledges at the same time his bondage to it, in private and public life, the only and perpetual obligation to redress, in order to his responsibilities and capacities all the privations of body and the soul that could disable or mutilate any human being, whoever he may be³⁶. Even though, obligation rises in each individual differently and in various manners and degrees of clarity, from mere rejection to rule of conduct, in that same extent, is good inserted in society.

The relationship with the collective works if it provides the necessary conditions for human development, it should be built in such a way, as to eliminate everything that could harm or impair the mysterious germination and development of the impersonal element of the soul³⁷.

Collectivities have no way to the impersonal. In the same way that a group of people cannot perform a mathematical addition. For a mathematical addition takes place in a single mind, which temporarily forgets the rest of the minds³⁸. Collectivity is confusing because it provides a false imitation of the impersonal: this is the error of idolatry. Let's not be confused, the human being cannot escape the collective until he rises over the personal, to break into the impersonal.

But the sort of men who could formulate such vindication things, the ones that have the monopoly of speech are the privileged ones. It is not them who would say that privilege is not worthwhile, they don't think that way; it would be indecent on their part. Many of the indispensable truths that would save men are not said because this sort of thing; the ones who could say them can't formulate them; the ones that can formulate them cannot say them. The solution to this wrong is one of the most urgent needs of today's politics³⁹. It is imperative to do away with institutions, costumes or habits that might lead to party spirit. Neither "personalities" nor parties attend truth or human misery.

- Your words sound quite dooming, Ms. Weil. Do you think there is a way out of this troubled perspective?

- Yes of course there is. Usually the most difficult problems have the simplest solutions.

The respect shown to the greatness of manhood is the basis of obligation. Obligation should be the kingpin of the law instead of rights (these can be objects of commerce). Obligations aim to the solution of worldly needs of the soul and of the body of any human being. To each need there is an obligation. Any other kind of obligation is misperception. I emphasize the impersonal over the collective. This is the kind of conscience awakening everyone who has seeped in the scope of the impersonal encounters, and at the same time develops a responsibility towards all humans: to protect in them, not the person but all that which the person covers of fragile possibilities of channeling to the impersonal. This is the only way of increasing the Good in the world and to redirect all actions toward transcendence.

Obligations are a solid social connectivity, it weaves solid but flexible networks among humans, who naturally tend to grow and improve through virtue, which truly has no limits, and opens opportunities (personal inspirations) unflinching because it is the true way to the GOOD.

³⁵ *Ibidem*.

³⁶ *Cfr. EL., p. 77-84.*

³⁷ *Selected Essays., Oxford University Press., London., 1962. p. 17.*

³⁸ *S.W., Ecrits de Londres et Derniere Lettres., Gallimard., Paris., 1957. pp 13.*

³⁹ *Cfr. EL., p. 42.*

- I feel relieved. So what you mean is that if everyone in a society takes responsibility of their obligations, which consist mainly in subsidizing their neighbor's needs, this society would not only be strong, but also straightened towards the impersonal transcendence. How does obligation bonds one individual to another?

- Exactly. Pretty much so. Besides this obligation lock, it keeps social structures simple and healthy not letting complicated ideological conceptions confuse thoughtful and down-to-earth and at the same time open-minded. It is an attainable solution, in which each one has to do individually: that is in society, not as collective.

There is a true distinction between rights and obligations. While rights need an established equality of forces to be effective, and favor the contingent aspect of personality in terms of means and ends of this equation, obligations accomplish true humanity in the subject and object at the same time, because real equality is acknowledged and promoted, even in the cases where this equality is not socially recognized. Therefore, individuals are bonded to each other in two ways: first everything worthy of respect must receive it; and second, this obligation prevails because every human being has an eternal destiny, being either subjects or objects of such respect. In this sense, as obligations are linked to our eternal destiny and because this destiny is universal they, concern each and every individual. The characteristic of good is to descend and satisfy the needs. In that case, the possibility to satisfy my own need of good may consist in my own good deeds toward others.

This, I must say, is humane and not beastly.

- I agree Ms. Weil. Proceeding in the analysis of this obligation-based society, what has to happen in the human mind to be in touch with the impersonal and don't lose the grip of reality. In other words,

3. - How can we grasp the concrete, practical-ethical choice of a single individual, which precedes any theory?

- In this order of ideas we will have to focus our attention in the very concrete and practical, the domain of theory of knowledge and the introduction of the eternal in time. Not an easy quest and words are not often accurate. But it is decisive.

As Plato mentions in *Timeous*, the sole light that continually falls from the sky provides the tree with enough energy to root deeply into the soil⁴⁰. The tree is really ingrained in the sky. Only that which comes from above can truly leave a mark on earth. This is precisely the way ethical action must be looked at. The pursuit of the absolute Good as a demand for human completion is the link each man has to this other reality, and anyone aware of that reality is aware of this bond as well. Realities in this world embody differences, and different objects require different kind of attentions, and therefore all men are different in relation to what grounds them to this world. But, in relation to the other reality, from where absolute Good comes from, all men are identical. This is the essential human structure, which is projected in the faculty that draws light over any other human being, and he who has this faculty whether he realizes it or not, has his attention set on this supranatural reality. Someone who is not yet determined to exclusive fidelity to this inner light installs lie in the center of his heart, and thus gets inner darkness. Lies, errors, and empty words are the thoughts of those who don't want truth, or want truth and something else; trying to cope truth to another fixed conception. To be resolved means understanding there is nothing to resolve, that existence has no meaning for the discursive faculties, these should be kept as the mere investigation instruments of intelligence to come in contact with a gross reality. It is the longing for Truth in the void, without trying to guess its content beforehand. This is precisely the mechanism of attention, it works undividedly, heeds one sole object, which, is the first condition for practical choice. Being attentive means to keep on looking until light is made, just as in sensible perception when we are not sure of what appears we move around but keep on looking... with time everything changes and if in spite of the undergone modifications our view persists, illusions disperse and the real appears. The condition is that attention should be a point of view not an attachment⁴¹. In this sense, what counts in a human life are not the events that happen in years, months, or even days, it is what links one minute to the next, and what it taxes in our body, in our heart, in our soul, but -above all- in the exercise of the faculty of attention to bring forth this concatenation⁴². In relation to any order, a superior one that is infinitely higher cannot be represented in the lower one except as an infinitely tiny, and so it works with an instant and eternity. Down here, the supranatural element is secret, silent, quasi-invisible, infinitely small but decisive⁴³. Nevertheless, the gap is a bond, the distance between the God and the creature is the possibility of ascension, and so is the distance of the Good and our action in the practical realm, this distance is our working space.

⁴⁰ E.L., p. 74 ss.

⁴¹ LPG., p. 122.

⁴² *La Condition Ouvriere.*, Gallimard., Paris., 1951. p. 168.

⁴³ S.W., *Opression et Liberte.*, Gallimard., Paris., 1955. p. 21.

Evil isn't but the distance between God and his creatures⁴⁴. Just like music develops in time and captures our attention stealing it from time, taking it every instant above of what it is, the wait is void and waits for the immediate, we don't wait for a note or a silence ceases to be, even though we cannot think of its continuation⁴⁵. So is our relation to the Good.

The pristine attention I am speaking about shall be detached from any other faculties. What is possible lies in the scope of imagination and consequently involves degradation, therefore we must desire either what exists or what cannot exist at all, better still, both things: what is and what can't be are both out of the becoming⁴⁶. I think this is a healthy way to keep ethical choice away of theories, and keep individual options simple and to a manageable immediate scope.

- With an enlightening intention I will reverse the question: How is our concrete existence penetrated by the supranatural?

- The natural part of the soul is forever submitted to necessity, just as the social aspect is, but "God throws a rope" to each one of us, just as a "castaway whipped over a waste amid turbulent seas", the one who "holds the rope, does not escape the buffeted" but these combine with the tension of the rope to form an ensemble with different mechanic behavior: "In the same way the supranatural cannot descend to the natural scope, nature nonetheless is transformed by the presence of the supranatural"⁴⁷. So it is the thirst of God the only impulse capable of provoking the ascension of the soul, in other words, the one who is not rooted in God is entirely at the mercy of chance. So, the bottom line is that man can only know and judge himself in reference to the supranatural, which, understood in this way, penetrates him and inhabits within. Without this, there is only infrahuman, the supranatural turns out to be the difference between the human and animal behavior: a difference infinitely miniscule⁴⁸.

-Now all the pieces of the puzzle are coming together. We shall now move forward in the realm of reflection, as to unravel the crossroads where thought turns to action. So, I ask you Ms. Weil:

4. - How can we reflect on this problem with the watchword »courage to act«?

- In order to put together the whole picture, I will start by defining the scope of each notion in order to clarify the influence of each, in the order of thought (reflection) and in the order of praxis (courage to act) to adjoin a healthy intertwine.

Intelligence is exercised by obedience when it faces the unintelligible⁴⁹. In a way, the supranatural is like the light, it enables sight but cannot be seen, in this sense the object of investigation cannot be the supranatural but this world, the supranatural is light, if it is objectivized, it is lessened as it is turned into a concept, turned in a content of thought and therefore limited, it loses all transcendence. Then in the scope of intelligence, the supranatural has a dark and a light source, it points to a particular kind of knowledge that comes from love and from a certain type of contact. Supranatural love contacts reality in a more perfect way than intelligence, and precisely that is perceived by intelligence itself, because if this contact did not exist, intelligence could not tell about it. The experience of the transcendent could appear as contradictory, nevertheless, it can only be known through contact⁵⁰. Thus, intelligence leads us beyond its realm. This would be knowledge without words, an experience quite strange now a days that things are bottled up into people through slogans⁵¹. The right use of words are not meant to correspond to any conceptions, since what they express is unconceivable such as God and Truth or Justice, Love and Good. For their use to be legitimate, it is necessary not to enclose them in human conceptions and only tie them to direct actions inspired by the light. Otherwise, they are clearly read as lies. In this line of reasoning but in an opposite way, it could be said that universal consensus indicates truth: Truth is one and Justice is one. But errors and injustices are variable *ad infinitum*, this is how men converge in the just and true, while lie and crime separate them indefinitely. Being union a material force, it can be expected to employ truth and justice, down here in this world, as a resource to make truth and justice stronger than crime and error.

- Could you elaborate some more on how do these big words get tied to actions inspired by light?

⁴⁴ Chiers., p. 230.

⁴⁵ Cfr. Cahiers., p. 192.

⁴⁶ Idem., p. 194.

⁴⁷ S.W., *Institutions Prechreiennes., Editions de la Colombe., Paris., 1951.* pp. 162-3.

⁴⁸ C.S. p. 126.

⁴⁹ Cahiers., p. 264.

⁵⁰ Idem. p. 134-135.

⁵¹ Idem, p. 167.

- This is exactly where all of these notions are intertwined directly to inspired actions.

The key word is work: physical work although painful, is not degradation. It is neither art, nor science but is another activity that has absolutely the same value because it opens the same possibility to access an impersonal (supranatural) form of attention. To the same extent but in a different way, physical work implies certain contact with the reality, the truth, and the beauty of the universe and with the eternal wisdom that constitutes its orderly harmony.

Physical work implies at its best a specific contact with the beauty of the world. For someone whose limbs are stricken by the effort of a hard *journee*, in which he has been submitted to the harshness of matter, he carries in his flesh like a thorn, the reality of the universe. The difficulty for him, lies in being able to look and love, if he succeeds he loves the real. In this sense, slavery is work deprived of the light of eternity, without poetry, without religion. Eternal light provides not a reason to live or work, but a fullness that dispenses searching for such a reason⁵².

Enlightened physical work and the development of art have very much in common, both awaken the close attention that enlightens the soul and move to metaxu.

The fact is that this big words guide us all the time, we just have to exercise the faculty to see them and the confidence to let that happen to us, in us, through us.

- How does this take place?

- We have stated before that obligation arouses in a soul that knows its way to be of service to others. To grasp the needs of others two elements are needed:

➤ One is metaxu, the insight of Good which we are personally capable of imprinting.

➤ Second: where to imprint good exactly: to whom, where, and how: the worldly component.

The practical path to achieve this is one and the same for the supranatural, but bifurcates in several lines of action. Four watch words lead the way: 1) the Good, that is the supranatural reality from where all the Truth, Beauty and Justice in this world descend from.

2) Justice; 3) Truth; 4) Beauty.

This notions are the answers⁵³ of the most pressing human needs, these experiences are methodologically the same, since they embrace⁵⁴ the dark and light⁵⁵ sides leading us to complete the circle of totality:

❖ Why am I harmed? - Calls for Justice.

To the extent that man loves the Good, he becomes apt to know and understand: this love is the source of all certainties⁵⁶. From this standing point many of our everyday activities are coated with a supranatural character. First, the faculty of supranatural love leads thought beyond intelligence, intelligence rests true to herself acknowledging the existence of this superior faculty in the soul, the transcendent can only be known through contact, our faculties cannot fabricate it⁵⁷: "The consented subordination of all the natural faculties to the soul, that is to the supranatural love, is FAITH: it is what Plato named JUSTICE in *The Republic*"⁵⁸.

Justice consists in watching that no harm is inflicted to any human being, harm is inflicted when someone shouts: "why am I being hurt?" In order to solve these problems, there is a need to coat the spirit of Truth and Justice, by any necessary means. Every human soul through the *Pater Noster* raises this prayer to God, "deliver me from evil", but God can preserve from evil the eternal part of the soul, which has come in true contact with Him, the rest of the soul, is abandoned to the will and vicissitudes of men, this is exactly the size of our obligation of Justice to men: a practical day to day issue. To see to it is the responsibility of each and every one of us.

❖ Why am I trapped in my own thought? - Calls for Truth.

Discursive thought is a means, which ends in a trap: if a spirit, a captive mind, ignores its captivity, it lives in error. The point is to get to the dead end of our own intelligence, to this limit situation and then cross to the other side: This is TRUTH. To think with the soul means to experience nothingness. The passage to truth is the soul's nakedness, this causes to the soul what death causes to flesh, and this is the pristine experience of Truth. Beware that the love for truth is always humble the real genius is the supranatural virtue of humbleness in the scope of thought.

This devouring thirst for truth is one of the implicit forms of love of God, which encloses the Good and the Beautiful, is the dazzling reality⁵⁹. Therefore, it is reality itself what we want to embrace, the

⁵² *Idem.*, p. 238.

⁵³ *Obligations when answered by someone.*

⁵⁴ *This is metaxu.*

⁵⁵ *The unintelligible and the worldly.*

⁵⁶ S.W., *La Source Grecque.*, Gallimard., Paris., 1953. p. 96.

⁵⁷ *C.*, II., P. 135-135.

⁵⁸ *C.S.*, p. 809.

⁵⁹ *Escrits Historiques et Politiques.*, Gallimard., Paris., 1960. p. 215.

instant of the embrace is the reward of the intellectual and moral *ascesis* that is the effort of living in the TRUTH. This is what I call the making of truth: truth is always practical⁶⁰.

❖ Why do I feel an infinite desire, and I don't want this to change? - Calls for Beauty.

Beauty down here is the supreme mystery. It is a resplendence that calls for attention but has no mobile to last. Beauty promises but never gives. It raises hunger but does not feed the part of the soul that seeks worldly satisfaction, it can only satisfy the part that looks, and contemplates. It raises desire, but makes us feel there is nothing to desire, because what it truly desires is that nothing changes: It is finality with no end. If we manage not to get out of the delicious torment she inflicts on us, desire can turn into love forming a seed in our faculty of attention. Beauty captures desire, empties it from its content but endows it with a present object, preventing us to jump into the future. It is the absolute here and now.

The eternal instant captured in all fine arts. This is where the power of sunrise and sunsets lies.

This glow of Beauty falls over misery due to the light that the spirit of Justice and Truth irradiate, this is what enables the human spirit to admire and imprint its true nature in this world. Everything that comes from pure Love is lighted by the radiance of beauty. Beauty is a sensible experience confusedly mixed with the limitations of the thought in which it is cloistered at first. Beauty is the experimental truth that incarnation is possible⁶¹. It is a sort of incarnation of God in the world (*Timeous*) of which Beauty is the sign⁶². The order of the world is the object of science, not of matter; so the object of the world should be conceived as *conditio sine qua non* of a rational creature, and therefore Providence is the real object of science⁶³.

- Quite illuminating. Please just make clear where does the courage to act come from?

- The courage to act is this internal energy, which we receive from the light of the Good just as an electrical phenomenon in which electrons go through with an incredible force in metaxu.

Being Justice, Truth and Beauty allied sisters with such wonderful words (in the sense of completeness), there is no need for any other force or courage. Accordingly, the fulfillment of an obligation is always a good everywhere; Truth, Beauty, Justice and Compassion are good always, everywhere.

The degree and proper nature of the suffering or nakedness of the soul differ widely amid human beings; this depends on the vital energy (courage) available at the starting point and the attitude developed through the suffering trance.

In relation to the false goods, desire and possession mismatch; in relation to the true good there is no discrepancy.

Good separated from bad is opposed to the universal laws of the universe just as the lighted object projects a shadow, if our thought oppose natural laws we'll be doomed to fall in disgrace. If we don't want to disperse this bad attached to the good we must be willing to concentrate it in ourselves, to absorb it, therefore the desire for pure and absolute Good implies the acceptance of personal affliction. Only God is the absolute Good, Creation that comes from God, but is other than God, is essentially good and bad⁶⁴ mixed together.

It is not by the way people speak about God but by the way they speak about the world that we know that a person has undergone the fire of the love of God that, his soul has been tempered. There is no possible disguise. There could be forgeries of the love of God, but there cannot be falsifications of the transformation of the soul He operates in the soul, we cannot have the slightest idea of such transformation other than passing through it⁶⁵.

- So, in other words, the kind of world we live in, depends on the profoundness of our supranatural relation to it, *n'est pas*?

To finish the interview, as an advice from beyond... I would like you to tell the audience what are the issues that in your opinion that should be taken care of by individuals and which should be addressed by politicians?

- To conceive obligations in a concrete way, toward human beings, and divide them in categories, it is enough to think in the worldly needs of the body and human soul. Human needs, as I have said, are sacred; their satisfactions cannot be subordinated to any reason of state or any other consideration,

⁶⁰ C.S., p. 84.

⁶¹ C., III., p. 62.

⁶² *Verbus ordenati*.

⁶³ C., III., p. 89.

⁶⁴ *Idem*, p. 28.

⁶⁵ C.S., p. 96.

whatever it may be. The only limit to the satisfaction of the needs of any human being could be the ones of other human beings. The limit is legitimate only in the case all human needs receive the same attention. It is only about worldly needs, since they are the only ones man can satisfy; when the soul's needs are not met, it finds itself in a similar state to a famished and mutilated body.

The human body has the need of: nourishment, warmth, sleep, hygiene, rest, exercise, and fresh air amongst others.

The needs of the soul are presented in pairs in order to be completed and balanced in each individual: -equality and hierarchy: equality refers to public recognition correctly expressed in costumes and institutions; hierarchy is the scale of responsibilities.

-Consented obedience and freedom: consented obedience is the one we give to an authority considered legitimate. It is not possible in case either of conquest, or *Coup d'Etat*, or economic power built on money. Freedom is the power to choose intimately in the margin opened by the forces of nature and the authority recognized as legitimate. This margin should be as wide for freedom not to be fictional, put applied only to innocent things, as not to permit certain kinds of crime to be licit.

- Truth and freedom of expression: the need for truth demands that everyone has access to the cultivation of the spirit, which culture consists of. It demands that no pressure in the scope of thought shall be exerted be it material or moral, that might come from an intention alien to truth, in this sense all propaganda must be banned. It demands protection from error and lie. It also demands that public health shall be kept from poisons in the field of thought. Intelligence needs exercise, so an independent field for intellectual investigation is necessary.

- Solitude and intimacy on one hand, social life on the other.

- Personal property other than money, more like appropriation of concrete objects, such as a house, the country, utensils, etc. that the soul may consider as its extensions of itself and her body. Justice demands that personal property be as inalienable as freedom is.

- The human soul needs punishment and honor: The first to return to the path of good, the second to be reinserted into society.

-Disciplined participation in a common chore of public value or utility, and personal initiative in such participation.

- The human soul needs both, security and risk. Fear to violence, to hunger, or any other extreme evil, are soul sicknesses. Boredom caused by lack of risk is also a soul's illness. The human soul needs to feel rooted in various natural and friendly environments to communicate with the universe through them: such as motherland, language, culture, history, profession, locality etc. Therefore, anything that deracinates, or prevents a human being from rooting is a crime.

The criterion by which we can measure that human needs are being satisfied is the expansion of fraternity, joy and beauty. If there is contraction, sadness or ugliness there are privations to attend⁶⁶: unhappiness predisposes the soul to receive avidly, to drink all that comes from above, it's the providers not the consumers that are needed for this product ⁶⁷.

For policy makers and politicians, they must comply with these obligations as a rule of conduct. Its violation shall be punished harshly. Institutions and costumes designed for this punishment shall be created, but this unfortunately, requires several generations.

- Very clear, your explanation is quite detailed, our audience is very grateful. And I think this long chat has guided us through the most important coordinates of your thought. Our channels are open for a new conversation anytime.

- Thank you for the opportunity of addressing other generations and letting me have a glimpse of future. Even though sadly, worldly things are not getting any better, clearly there is much more Good in it, and a very big critical mass is working on it.

I wonder if you care to comment something about the thinkers who have influenced your very profound an eloquent way to see and be reality?

- Plato. Blaise Pascal,

Idealist philosophy taught by Alain founded by Kant, Descartes and Palto

Albert Camus

Proudhon, Boris Souvarine (Fundador del partido comunista frances PFC), Pareto, Max Weber, Georg Simmel,

Mas cerca de las ideas ecologistas actuales: Un llamado a los seres libres porque solo la libertad engendra la libertad.

La decepcion generada por el fracas de la esperanza revolucionaria

⁶⁶ S.W., *Profession of Faith. In E.L.*, p. 80-84.

⁶⁷ *ELetDL.*, p. 15.c

La vuelta a la religiosidad se debio quiza a la desilusion del planteamiento revolucionario marxista